

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

EMI NAGIOS v. 3.0.0

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EMI NAGIOS

General Documentation

Functional Description

EMI Nagios metapackage is a package providing through its dependencies the whole collection of EMI's products nagios probes

Software Requirement Specification

The Nagios probe specification can be found at
<http://nagios.sourceforge.net/docs/nagioscore/3/en/pluginapi.html>

Development

Programming Languages

Probes can be developed in any of these languages:

- Python (2.4)
- Perl (5.8) - in case of Perl usage of module Nagios::Plugin is highly recommended.
- C
- shell scripting (Bash, Bourne)

Nagios Conditions

- Each probe must provide the following arguments:

```
-h help (--help)
-t timeout (--timeout)
```

- The following arguments should be used if applicable:

```
-H hostname (--hostname)
-p port (--port)
-u url (--url)
-v verbose (--verbose)
-w warning threshold (--warning)
-c critical threshold (--critical)
```

- Limit for a Nagios Test/Plugin output: Maximum output size is 16KB. Above that limit the output will be truncated.

More details on EGI Nagios Probes Development -
<https://tomtools.cern.ch/confluence/display/SAMDOC/Probes+Development>

System Administrator Documentation

System Administrator Guide

Installation and configuration

Repositories needed for the installation of emi-nagios metapackage together with all EMI products nagios plugins

- OS repository (SL5/x86_64 or SL6/x86_64)
- EPEL repositories (EPEL5 or, respectively, EPEL6)
- EMI repositories:
 - ◆ you can find more information on what are and how to enable their use at:
 - ◇ https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/EMI/GenericInstallationConfigurationEMI2#The_middle
-for EMI 2 version
 - ◇ https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/EMI/GenericInstallationConfigurationEMI3#The_middle
- for EMI 3 version
- EGI-SAMMonitoring repository:
 - ◆ <http://rpm.hellasgrid.gr/mash/centos5-egee/> - for SL5/x86_64
 - ◆ <http://rpm.hellasgrid.gr/mash/centos6-egi-sam/> - for SL6/x86_64 (work-in-progress)

Installation

```
# yum install emi-nagios
```

will install all available EMI nagios probes:

- emi-cream-nagios
- emi-lb-nagios-plugins
- emi-wms-nagios
- nagios-plugins-argus
- nagios-plugins-bdii
- nagios-plugins-dpm-disk
- nagios-plugins-dpm-head
- nagios-plugins-ees
- nagios-plugins-fts
- nagios-plugins-glexec
- nagios-lcgdm
- nagios-plugins-lcgdm
- nagios-plugins-lcgdm-common
- nagios-plugins-lfc
- nagios-plugins-voms
- nordugrid-arc-nagios-plugins
- unicore-nagios-plugins

Other emi-nagios dependencies:

- glite-yaim-core
- glite-yaim-clients
- fetch-crl

The following probe:

- nagios-plugins-emi.glexec

is part of gLExec-wn, the emi-glexec-wn metapackage, and is installed directly on the WN.

Changes planned for EMI 3:

- nagios-plugins-emi.glexec and nagios-plugins-emi.ees will be RENAMED in *nagios-plugins-glexec* and *nagios-plugins-ees*, and will be installed in `%{_libdir}/nagios/plugins/`, i.e. `/usr/lib64/nagios/plugins/` for RPM, location used by Fedora, and in `/usr/lib/nagios/plugins` for Debian.

Configuration & Usage of individual services nagios probes

For the configuration of the environment of the EMI-NAGIOS:

```
# /opt/glite/yaim/bin/yaim -d 6 -c -s site-info.def -n NAGIOS
```

with a very basic site-info.def, for ex:

```
# cat site-info.def
PX_HOST=emitb2.ics.muni.cz
BDII_HOST=certtb-bdii.cern.ch
USERS_CONF=/root/siteinfo/users.conf
GROUPS_CONF=/root/siteinfo/groups.conf
BDII_DELETE_DELAY=0
# Site-wide settings
SITE_NAME="emi-testbed-cnaf"
SITE_DESC="EMI Integration Testbed site INFN-CNAF"
SITE_SUPPORT_EMAIL="root@localhost"
SITE_SECURITY_EMAIL="root@localhost"
SITE_LOC="Bologna, Italy"
SITE_WEB="http://www.italiangrid.it/"
SITE_LAT=42.0
SITE_LONG=11.0
VOS="testers.eu-emi.eu testers2.eu-emi.eu cms dteam infngrid"
```

For the configuration of the probes - please have a look at the individual EMI products nagios probes documentation

- ARC
 - ◆ http://www.nordugrid.org/arc/releases/13.02/release_notes_13.02.html#nagios - Release Notes v. 1.5.0
 - ◆ download and install the latest version of nordugrid-arc-nagios-plugins-doc available in EMI repositories
 - ◇ you can have have a look at nordugrid-arc-nagios-plugins-doc-1.5.0
- ARGUS
 - ◆ <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/EGEE/ArgusEMINagiosProbes>
- DPM/LFC
 - ◆ <https://svnweb.cern.ch/trac/lcgdm/wiki/Dpm/Admin/Monitoring/Probes>
- EMI EES
 - ◆ `"/usr/lib(64)/nagios/plugins/check_ees --help"` will offer all the details needed
- L&B
 - ◆ <http://egee.cesnet.cz/cvsweb/LB/LBTP.pdf> - Chapter 7 "Nagios Probe"
- gLEXec-wn
 - ◆ `"/usr/lib64/nagios/plugins/check_glexec --help"` will offer all the details needed
- Nagios probes to monitor CREAM and WN
 - ◆ <https://wiki.italiangrid.it/twiki/bin/view/CREAM/NagiosProbes>
- UNICORE
 - ◆ <http://unicore-dev.zam.kfa-juelich.de/documentation/nagios-probes-2.3.2/manual.pdf>
- VOMS
 - ◆ <https://github.com/italiangrid/voms-nagios/blob/master/README.md> - included in the nagios-plugins-voms package
- WMS
 - ◆ <https://wiki.italiangrid.it/twiki/bin/view/WMS/WmsProbe>

Service Reference Card

- EMI Nagios Service Reference Card

Direct link to this twiki: - <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/EMI/EMINagios>

-- DoinaCristinaAiftimiei - 10-May-2012

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